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**DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONSTRUCTION OF A MATERIAL PIPELINE FOR
PNEUMATIC TRANSPORT OF COTTON
РАЗРАБОТКА КОНСТРУКЦИИ МАТЕРИАЛОПРОВОДА ДЛЯ
ПНЕВМОТРАНСПОРТА ХЛОПКА**

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается эффективность пневмотранспортного устройства, предназначенного для транспортировки хлопка в хлопчатобумажной промышленности. Пропускная способность пневматической трубы зависит от ее диаметра, материала трубы, скорости потока, аэродинамических свойств хлопка и конструкции входного отверстия трубы. Рекомендуется изготовить входное отверстие трубы в виде конуса, что способствует снижению ее аэродинамического сопротивления, увеличению пропускной способности трубопровода и использованию труб меньшего диаметра по сравнению с существующим.

Ключевые слова. Хлопок, пневмотранспорт, производительность, давление воздуха, скорость воздуха, воздушный поток, аэродинамический режим, компрессор, динамическое давление, статическое давление, коэффициент трения хлопка, воздушная смесь, дискретная фаза.

Abstract. The article deals with the efficiency of pneumatic transport device designed for the transportation of cotton in the cotton industry. The material carrying capacity of a pneumatic tube depends on its diameter, pipe material, flow rate, aerodynamic properties of the cotton, and the design of the pipe inlet. It is recommended to manufacture the pipe inlet in the form of a cone, which helps to reduce its aerodynamic resistance, increase the throughput capacity of the pipeline and use pipes of a smaller diameter relative to the existing one.

Keywords. Cotton, pneumatic transport, capacity, air pressure, air speed, air flow, aerodynamic mode, compressor, dynamic pressure, static pressure, friction coefficient of cotton, air mixture, discrete phase.

Introduction. Theoretical researches have shown that there are a number of unutilized opportunities in the transportation of cotton by air. In particular, due to the irregular supply of cotton to the pneumatic transport, the diameter of the air duct was taken much larger than the calculated values so that the air duct does not clog during operation. During research of the air duct capacity, it was found that the air duct with a diameter of 400 mm could pass up to 60 tons of cotton per hour. In the cotton gin industry today, the labour productivity of 10-15 tons/hour is sufficient, since the maximum productivity of production machines does not exceed 15 tons/hour. It is theoretically justified that air ducts with a diameter of 355 mm and 315 mm are sufficient to ensure such performance. This requires that the cotton be delivered

regularly to the air transport equipment. We have argued that this problem can be solved by improving the working parts of the machine that spoils the cotton gin, and by feeding the cotton into the air pipe using a pneumatic mechanical feed.

Problem statement. Another problem is the high aerodynamic drag of the pipe inlet, which prevents the free flow of cotton into the pipe, reducing its permeability and causing accumulation. While entering the pipe, the mixture of air and cotton must overcome the resistance force of the pipe inlet. This force is created by the air itself entering the pipe. Practice has shown that when air enters into the pipe, the transverse surface of the jet narrows and a gap arises between the flow and the wall of the pipe, as well as an air vortex in this cavity. This prevents air and material from entering the pipe.

We analyse the motion of a two-component medium consisting of a mixture of air and cotton particles in the initial part of an pneumatic conveying pipeline (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Movement of air and cotton particles at the inlet of the air pipe.

From figure, the pieces of cotton (discrete medium) pass between the motionless air particles and enter the zone of influence of air pressure. Here, first, the vacuum force in the air duct pulls it into the air pipe.

The impact force (impulse) of the air particles also affects the cotton particles as they fall into the flowing airway, and as a result, the cotton particles mix with the air particles and begin to move towards the air pressure (vacuum) source inside the air pipe. As it moves faster, it occurs as if air particles are leaking through stationary bodies, and frictional forces with air particles on the surface of the cotton pieces, as well as frictional forces between the inner surface of the pores and the air particles because the cotton raw material is a porous material. To overcome these resistance forces, the reaction forces created by the air particles try to move the cotton in its own direction of motion.

From fig. 1, the narrowing of the flow is indicated by a black line, the transverse measurement of the flow is noticeable, the narrowing of the air pipe from the diameter d to the diameter of the small d_c .

Reference [1] shows that the corridor in the air duct is $d_c = 0.5 d$, that is, the air duct is reduced by half of its internal diameter. To eliminate this condition, it was recommended to expand the mouth of the air pipeline under a certain radius or to prepare it in the form of a cone [2,3].

Figure 2. Construction of air pipe inlet.

Problem solution. The most rational narrowing angle is 60 degrees [4,5,6] (Fig. 2). On the recommendation of E. Stefanov [7], we developed an algorithm for preparing the inlet of the pipe for pipes of different diameters to reduce aerodynamic drag and determined its required dimensions.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} AC &= b_k = BC \cos 30; \\ AB &= BC = b_k \sin 30 / \cos 30 = b_k / \sqrt{3} \\ BC &= b_k / \cos 30 = 2 b_k / \sqrt{3}; (3.41) \\ D &= BE = 2 AB + d = 2 b_k / \sqrt{3} + d. \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Where b_k is the narrowing distance of the air pipe inlet, **mm**; α - angle of narrowing, **grad**; d is the diameter of the air pipe, **mm**. According to the drawing, $90 - \alpha = 30$ degrees. In that case, if one angle of the ABC triangle is 90 degrees, the third angle will be 60 degrees.

Accordingly, in order to reduce the aerodynamic resistance of the air pipe inlet, it is necessary to fasten a cone with height $b_k = 0.2d$, small base d , large base $2 b_k / \sqrt{3} + d$. It follows from this, if the diameter of the air pipe:

- 400 mm, cone with height $b_k = 0.2 d = 80$ mm, small base $d = 400$ mm, large base $D = 2 b_k / \sqrt{3} + d = 492$ mm;
- 355 mm, cone with height $b_k = 0.2 d = 71$ mm, small base $d = 355$ mm, large base $D = 2 b_k / \sqrt{3} + d = 437$ mm;
- 315 mm, cones with height $b_k = 0.2 d = 63$ mm, small base $d = 315$ mm, large base $D = 2 b_k / \sqrt{3} + d = 388$ mm will be required.

The next problem with pipe construction is to ensure that the movable pipes are hermetically fixed when they are interconnected and that the inner surface of the pipe remains flat. To solve this problem, we developed the following technical solution (Figure 3): 2 cones (2) for one pipe are made in a single template, the same shape and size, and fastened to both ends of the pipe (1), facing one side. Since the small base of the cone is made equal to the diameter of the pipe, when both cones are fastened to one side, one end is funnel-shaped, the other end is wedge-shaped, and when connected with another such pipe, the inner surface of the pipe remains flat [8,9]. This creates an air duct in the new design. The figure below shows the method of fastening the cones to the pipe (performed by welding), the method of interconnection of two pipes in the middle, the figure below shows the interconnected position of 3 pipes.

Figure 3. Scheme of forming an air pipe and a portable pneumatic track with conical ends.

By connecting such air ducts to each other, it is possible to create a route of any length. If the outside of the cone and the inside of the funnel are coated with a sealant, it will be possible to ensure high tightness when connecting the air ducts. As a sealant can be used rubber glue, oil paint, as well as clay made of ordinary fine-grained soil in the operating environment.

During operation, the air duct is lifted by means of brackets (3), moved from place to place, and, if necessary, fitted and fastened to each other by adjusting the conical part of one to the conical part of the other. Such preparation of air duct joints allows ensuring the tightness of the air ducts, reducing the absorption of air from the outside through the joints. If the cones are made of high precision, high-quality material and fastened at the required level, it will be possible to eliminate air absorption. Also, the conical shape of the air pipe mouth prevents excessive compression of the air flow entering the air pipe and reduces the resistance of the air pipe mouth to material and air ingress [10,11]. This reduces congestion at the mouth of the pipe and increases the reliability of pneumatic conveying operation.

Conclusion

1. The efficiency of a pneumatic conveying device designed to transport cotton in a ginning plant depends on its air consumption, the reduction of which allows the device to reduce energy consumption.

2. The material carrying capacity of a pneumatic conveying pipe depends on its diameter, the material of the pipe (i.e. the coefficient of friction of the cotton on the inner surface of the pipe), the airflow rate, the aerodynamic properties of the cotton pieces, as well as the pipe construction.

3. To reduce the aerodynamic resistance of the pipe inlet, it is recommended to prepare it in the form of a cone. This in turn increases the capacity of the pipe and allows the use of smaller diameter pipes than the practice. As a result, the air and energy consumption of pneumatic conveying decreases.

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